

Σουρεγεθης/Συρεγεθης (Souregethēs/Suregethēs) means “Holder (of the Spear)”=“Spear Holder” (Gethes=spear) & was another name of the Thracian Horseman, as well as an epithet of Ares, the spear-holder; the Mysian/Bythinian deity Syrgastas also meant “Spear-Holder” (Gastas=spear); Getae comes from the same root as the spear word, but didn’t mean “spear(men)”; Ketus was named for being the northern constellation that some believed drove (pricked, goaded) the Axis Mundi; Daki/Daci is cognate with Albanian Dak, “big ram”, & that Alb. Dak actually comes from “to drive, to lead” as in the bellwhether ram of the flock

Alexandru Gheorghiu
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The Thracian theonym Souregethēs/Suregethēs is attested in Philippi and Durostorum and elsewhere.

Souregethēs/Suregethēs according to the previous scholars was something like the Thracian Horseman deity who carried a spear with which he slew a dragon (and maybe identical to the Thracian Horseman, according to previous scholars, there is not much known so they weren’t sure; I have come to the conclusion that Souregethēs/Suregethēs is another name for the Thracian Horseman) and also somewhat like Dionysus and/or Silenos: Souregethēs/Suregethēs was a spring-time god, associated with drinking (especially symposium drinking-gatherings), spring-time feasting and feasting/drinking for the deceased (during spring-time; the flowers that arise to bloom for a bit only to vanish being symbols of often-fleeting human life). I’m sure that, from the Syrgastas evidence and Thracian Horseman evidence one can see online, Souregethēs/Suregethēs was a Sun-God like the Thracian Horseman, and both of them overlap with the springtime functions of Dionysus, as well as having some things in common with Dionysus which I may detail next time.

In Thrace there is also attested Suregethēs as an epithet of Ares, god of war¹. This proves that Suregethēs/ Souregethēs meant “Spear-Holder”. This Thracian *Soure/Sure* meaning “holder” derives from PIE **twerH*, “to enclose firmly, to hold firmly, to grasp tightly; firm, solid, hard”, as probably does Thracian Thiurdos/Surdos, which likely meant “holder”, so that Zibelthiurdos/Zibelthiurdus/Zbelsurdos likely meant “Lightning-Holder” and “Spear-holder” at the same time.

For my equation Ares Suregethēs=Ares Spear-Holder, see how Ares is stereotypically depicted holding a spear, and consider these lines from Homeric Hymn 8 to Ares (trans. Evelyn-White) (Greek epic 7th to 4th centuries BC):

“Ares, exceeding in strength, chariot-rider, golden-helmed, doughty in heart, shield-bearer, Saviour of cities, harnessed in bronze, strong of arm, unwearying, mighty with the spear, O defence of Olympus...”

¹ For Ares Suregethēs, see Najdenova, V. (1987), “A Shrine of Ares Suregethes in Thrace”, *Terra Antiqua Balcanica*, II:252-258. .

In Bithynia/Mysia, there is a deity attested as Syrgastas, Syrgastes: here Syr/Sur is again from PIE **twerH*, “to enclose firmly, to hold firmly, to grasp tightly; hard, firm, solid”, and Gastas/Gastes is from PIE **ǵʰasto-* (“branch ~ spear, sharp spine”) : I ask the reader to search for that root online or in a book and see all the cognates for themselves. Syrgastas/Syrgastes was often an epithet of Zeus, because the lightning-god and sun-god were closely associated in IE culture and some other cultures: see also how in European and Caucasian tradition, the prophet Elijah is associated with the sun-chariot and with the lightning-god. The Lydian attestation *Srkasta* is probably a loan from Mysian Syrgastas, and though I’ve seen an etymology proposing a connection to a Luwian *sarku-* word, that proposal is very erroneous, because we are 100% dealing instead with Syr+Gastas and in Lydian Sr+Kastas.

Awhile ago I came to the conclusion that *Getai* and *-gethēs* in some Thracian anthroponyms (see the anthroponyms in a later paragraph in this section) and in that Thracian theonym are cognate with Old Greek γήθυον (*gēthuon*) / γήτειον (*gēteion*) / κητίον (*kētíon*) =”onion/a kind of onion”, which most likely comes from the meaning “pungent, sharp, pricking” referring to how a fresh-cut onion especially is so pungent that it brings tears to the eyes. I thought about this probably a year or two before I published my first draft in July 2023 (I always prefer to derive onion words from “sharp, pungent” rather than from “ball; swollen” or “compact, firm” or some other meaning), but I wasn’t satisfied with thinking that *Ketos* meant “fanged” or “horned”; but in January 2024 or earlier I realized that Old Greek κῆτος (*kētōs*)=”whale; sea-monster; abyss”: most likely derives primarily from “driver (of the axis pole)”, the one that makes the north pole spin, moving the stars around as time passes (in actuality it is the earth that is revolving, not the constellations): see my 2024 work on the etymology of *Artemis* for all the details about that.

Meanwhile the meaning “abyss” for κῆτος (*kētōs*)=”whale; sea-monster; abyss” comes from “place where such deep-sea creatures dwell” and possibly also from the empty black region of space in the night sky above the north pole area, a region often compared to the smoke-hole in the top of a tent in cultures that mostly lived in tents/urts. Another possibility is “sharp, pointed” leading “a hollowing out as if done by a sharp object”: perhaps the celestial smoke-hole was thought of as having been gouged out by *Ketos* (with his tusks, fangs and/or horns; “fanged”/”tusked”/”horned”/”injurious” would have been very likely additional meanings of *Ketos* besides the primary meaning “Driver”; see also the winter/northern constellation *Capricorn* which is half-fish, half goat with horns) in the northern sky.

κητώεις=”full of hollows; cavernous” comes from the same ideas described in the previous sentence; and the meaning “phalanx” attested for κητώεις surely comes from “large body (of soldiers) armed with spears”, likening a large body of soldiers armed with spears to a large sea-beast armed with tusks, fangs and horns.

Some Old Greek words that are considered by consensus to derive from PIE **twerH-* are: σύρω = “to pull, drag”, deriving either from “force/strength applied to pull/drag” or from the earlier meaning “rope, cord used to pull/drag”, with “rope, cord” deriving from “to bundle tightly<to grasp firmly/enclose firmly”, which brings us to another Old Greek word deriving from PIE **twerH-*: the word σείρᾱ /σειρή / σηρά meaning “rope, cord” and in Koine Greek “chain”; and Σειρήν (*Seirén*) the source of *Siren*, most likely deriving from “entangler, binder”, from PIE **twerH-*, “to grasp firmly, enclose firmly”. Additional Old Greek words from **twerH-* include σορός=”urn, coffin” and

σαρδών="the rope sustaining the upper edge of a hunting-net" and σύρην="dragging, in a long line; dragged along": for both of these latter two, note the very close formal similarity to Thracian Surdos/Siurdos (despite the highly divergent meanings from the same root) extracted from Zibelsiurdos/Zibelsurdos (along with additional variants attested), and note how close in form Old Greek σάρω = "to pull, drag" is to Thracian Sure/Soure="holder". In other IE languages besides Greek, there are of course words from the root *twerH- which mean "to hold" as seen in Thracian, and I ask the reader to look that up for themselves until the next edition.

The name of the Daco-Thracian Getae people (singular: Γέτης (Gētēs); plural: Γέται (Gétai); another inflection is Γέτας (Gētās)) meant 1) "Drivers/Leaders" most likely, and could have also had additional meanings, including: 2) "fierce, wild" (from "pricked, goaded into anger and fierceness", a semantic shift that is well-attested in iE and Non-IE languages); 3) Energetic (from "pricked, stimulated"); 4) Herders (of various animals, sheep, cattle, goats) and this was probably the original meaning, later shifting to "Leaders/Drivers (of men; in the world of mankind)"; 5) Inspired (from "pricked, stimulated" by the Muses/Divinity/Divinities) 6) Injurers, from "pointed, sharp"; 7) Smart (from "pointed, sharp, acute").

The Thracian anthroponym Getas (recorded as the name of a South Thracian king on coinage issued by his kingdom) probably meant "Leader", from "Driver".

I don't think that Getae meant "wolves" nor "sea-monsters/dragons", but those options are not impossible since there is an Ancient Greek painting on a ceramic object with shows Cetus/Ketus as a giant sea-serpent with a wolf-head; and the Dacian Draco emblem has been described as a dragon with the head of a wolf.

The gethēs/getēs variation in Thracian anthroponyms (Zi-gethēs, Pari-getēs etc.) and the [th ~ t] variation in Old Greek γήθιον (gēthuon) / γήτειον (gēteion) / κητίον (kētíon) ="onion/a kind of onion"; so most likely gethēs is a variant of getēs (seen in Pari-getēs etc.) and of Gētēs/Gétai and Getas.

Now to consider three Thracian anthroponyms with either Gethes/Getes or Geto-: the three anthroponyms are Zigethēs (attested at least once in Kraynitsa near Blagoevgrad in Bulgaria): this name probably meant "Spear (guided by) Zeus"; Parigetēs (attested at least once in Batkun near Pazardjik in Bulg.); Getomousēs (attested in Olbia, either the Pontic Olbia or the Bythinian Olbia). I may decipher the these latter two in an upcoming edition.

The Gethousa of Sarmizegethousa (with a number of variants, Zarmisegethousa, etc.) probably referred to a deity identified as the driver of the sky's/earth's rotation on its axis, a deity identified closely with sun and with the storm/lightning god.

Gethousa surely had the additional meaning "of the Getae": Sarmi most likely meant "fortress", cognate to a Sanskrit Sarme that meant "fortress; strongly built structure" (I think this identification with this Sanskrit word has already been noted by a previous scholar). The portion ~ze~ may have meant "of": so we would have Sarmizegethousa="Fortress of the Getae" (which is exactly what it was their main fortress and the one whose fall led to the Dacians/Getae being conquered by the Romans) and likely also "Fortress of Gethousa", a deity (probably a goddess) as described above.

Part 2: Daci/Daki and Albanian Dak, "big ram"; Dawi/Davi/Daoui; and the term Dava found in Dacian toponyms and some Thracian toponyms.

I'll detail this section much more in my next edition. It's actually certain, even though I may not be able to make it sound certain in this edition.

First point, most important: Vladimir Orel was wrong in deriving Albanian Dak ("big ram") from PIE *d^hew- "to breathe; breath; soul", despite Albanian Dash meaning "ram" most likely deriving from PIE *d^hwes "to breathe; breath; soul; spirit; creature"

Instead, I posit that there was a root (perhaps Pre-IE/Non-IE) *dew-/*dew-k- (this reconstruction may be updated later) meaning "pointed, sharp", from which derive quite a number of Balkanic/Ancient Greek and some Italic words.

Ancient Greek Dapurinthos/Labyrinthos (the D/L variation happens a lot with this set of words I'm describing) derives from*dew- (vowel yet to be determined; maybe not the E vowel; and final consonant or consonants yet to be determined: may not have been "w") like so: "pointed">"to drive, to set in motion>to turn, revolve": from "to turn" comes the windings of the labyrinth maze. The semantic shifts "pointed>to goad>to drive" and "to drive, to set in motion>to turn, revolve" are well-known in linguistics, and the shift from "to turn" to the turnings of a maze requires no explanation.

Illyrian Deuadai="satyrs" is from *dew="pointed", because (as a semantic parallel, not from *dew I think) we find in Ancient Greek a word *tituros* which means "1) satyr; 2) big bellwether ram that leads the flock; 3) shepherd, goatherd; 4) reed, pipe. It is known in other instances where words for thin reeds come from "pointed", and meanings 2 and 3 require no explanation (from "pointed>to goad>to drive, to lead") and that leaves Satyr: they must have been viewed as the chiefs/leaders of the goats, and there were additional things intended as well probably, which I may discuss next time.

I posit additionally that Dacian Dava/Deva/Dova etc. (and very importantly, attested in Hesychius with the spelling Leba, which is not a manuscript error) which are found as the last component of many Dacian toponyms and some Thracian toponyms---come from this semantic shift from the same root as Dapurinthos: "pointed>to goad>to drive, to set in motion>to turn, to revolve>to revolve around, and therefore to sojourn, to dwell: this last semantic shift is quoted verbatim from an identical semantic shift encountered in the PIE root *k^wel- from which comes Latin colo meaning "to inhabit" and Ancient polos meaning "axis, axis pole, pole, the North Pole" and so on.

Cognate to Dacian Dava as well is Carian Labrus (axe) which is from "sharp, pointed" and/or from "pointed>to goad>to drive>to propel>to throw" referring to throwing-axes in battle. Those semantic shifts are attested in Sanskrit and elsewhere as well.

Ancient Greek laure (a ditch, an alley etc.) is another cognate, from "to cut a trench, to cut a ditch". Latin Laurus/Daurus/Dacrus (three variants) meaning "laurel tree" (source of English "laurel") is either from "to turn" leading to "wreath (the laurel wreath)" or referring to the pungent smell: most likely both qualities established these words applying to the laurel tree. The Ancient Greek equivalents (Daphne, and the variants) are cognates as well.

Obrador-Cursach Phrygian recently published a paper posting that Laqrisha in Lydian meant "tree": I think that is correct and derives from "pole" (see polos above) or from being hit by thrown lightning (see "to throw" above) or getting cut by axes (see Carian Labrus=axe).

As we see in Latin Daurus and Dacrus, so we find in Dacian Daci and Dawi/Davi (in Greek Daoi because by that time they usually did not render the W sound): so I posit that Daci/Daki had the same meanings as Getae that I described above, and Dawi/Davi/Daoi had the same meanings as Daci/Daki. The similarity to Phrygian daos/dawos="wolf" is a coincidence.

Believe it or not, before I found Albanian Dak meaning "big ram" I wrote in my notebooks a year earlier that Daki/Daci/Dawi/Davi/Daoi is cognate to Latin Daurus/Dacrus and Ancient Greek dapurinthos/laburinthos etc., but then I found Albanian Dak and I published another theory: but this

new explanation is the real one. I may not have described it as convincingly as I wanted, but I intend to do so in the upcoming editions.

Part 3.

Another key point of my findings is that, as the evidence in this paper quite strongly shows, Gétēs/Gétai was from a native Thracian word, not a Scythian/Iranic loan: the Scythians may have had a close cognate in their language, or they borrowed the word from Thracians. Possibly, the Scythians/Sarmatians did not use the term at all, and the ethnonyms Tyragetae, Massagetae and Thysogetae were only exonyms given by the Thracians to Scytho-Sarmatian peoples, and passed on to Greeks and Romans and to others in Europe.

Here follow some notes on whether the -getae in the ethnonyms Massagetae and Thysogetae (and maybe even Tyragetae, though since the Tyragetae were so close to the Getae, it seems more likely that the terms are cognates: but maybe not) are not cognate to Thracian Gétēs/Gétai and are only coincidentally similar to the Thracian terms Gétēs/Gétai.

The Iranologist Rüdiger Schmitt notes that although the original name of the Massagetae is unattested, it appears that the most plausible etymon is the Iranian **Masyaka-tā*. **Masyaka-tā* would be the plural form, containing the East Iranian suffix *-tā, which is reflected in Greek -tai. The singular form would be **Masi̇a-ka-*, composed of the Iranian *-ka- and **masi̇a-*, meaning "fish," derived from Young Avestan *masiia* cognate with Vedic *mátsya*. The name would literally mean "concerned with fish," or "fisherman." This corresponds with the remark made by the ancient Greek historian Herodotus (1.216.3) that "they live on their livestock and fish." Schmitt notes that objections to this reasoning, based on the assumption that, instead of *masi̇a-*, a derivation from Iranian **kapa-* "fish" (compare Ossetian *кæф* (*kæf*)) would be expected, is "not decisive."

The Iranologist János Harmatta has, however, criticised the proposal of *Massagetai*'s derivation from *masyaka-ta*, meaning "fish-eating (men)," as being semantically and phonologically unacceptable, and instead has suggested that the name might be derived from an early Bactrian language name *Maššagatā*, from an earlier *Mašyagatā* related to the Young Avestan terms *mašā-*, *mašīa-*, *mašīāka-* meaning "men," with the ending of the name being derived from the East Iranian suffix *-tā or from the collective formative syllable from which the suffix evolved. According to Harmatta's hypothesis, the Bactrian name *Maššagatā* would have corresponded to the name *Dahā*, meaning "men", used by the Massagetae for themselves.

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